

EFFECTS OF CRYSTALLIZATION ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLY(ETHER ETHER KETONE) COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY Carbon fibre reinforced poly (ether ether ketone) (C-PEEK) is an advanced thermoplastic composite. PEEK is one of a new generation of engineering polymers having good high temperature properties. PEEK is a semicrystalline thermoplastic polymer, that so with heat treatments, it is possible to get transcrySTALLINE interphase which is very important for material performance. In this study, we observed the % crystallization and transcrySTALLINE layer formation effects after heat treatments on the mechanical performance of C-PEEK composites.

KEYWORDS: C-PEEK, crystallinity, WAXD, fracture toughness, bending test

INTRODUCTION

PEEK is a high performance, semicrystalline thermoplastic. Its relatively stiff backbone gives excellent high temperature stability. It has a high glass transition temperature (145°C), high melting point (340°C) and a high continuous service temperature with the advantages of easy process ability by injection molding and other techniques common to thermoplastic polymers (1,2,3).

The mechanical properties of thermoplastic matrix composites depend significantly on the microstructure parameters, such as the degree and type of crystals. The size of the spherulites are controlled by controlling the heat treatment during the manufacturing of composites (4-6) and by the microstructure of the fibre which determines the ability to develop a transcrySTALLINE layer (7). There are several indications that slow-cooled or annealed materials, which have a fully developed crystalline structure, exhibit better mechanical properties (8). Likewise the presence of transcrySTALLINITY was shown to influence the mechanical performance through its effect on fibre / matrix bonding and on the stress transfer mechanism (9, 10).

It is possible to control the microstructure, especially the crystallinity of a part fabricated from PEEK by using suitable heating and cooling cycles. It is already well known that there is an

important relationship between crystallinity and mechanical properties. The level of crystallinity also effects the resistance to hostile environments, moreover achieving a desired level of mechanical response above the glass transition temperature is also influenced by the level of crystallinity. Of course, not only does of degree of crystallinity effect the mechanical properties but the detailed morphology of the crystalline phase will also be important (11).

The role of fibre / matrix interphase in composite materials is currently the focus of an increasing number of studies. An interphase is a third, relatively thick, intermediary phase present between constituents. Its elastic and mechanical properties are specifically designed to produce a certain effect on the overall performance of the composite material.

This paper reports the effect of various heat treatments at different temperatures and different times on mechanical properties of carbon fibre reinforced Poly (ether ether ketone) composites.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

Material

In this study, cross-ply carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composites were produced according to manufacturer (ICI, UK) suggestions from prepregs by using hot pressing technique and the details were given elsewhere (12). Composites were produced at 380°C. These samples have around 19 % crystallinity.

Heat Treatment

Three different heat treatments are applied to the samples. Table 1 shows the heat treatments applied at various temperature for different times. In Isothermal crystallization and annealing, there are two crystallization points. The first is the carbon fibre which is the strongest one and the second is the crystalline areas of PEEK matrix. But in quench samples, because of the amorphous matrix there is only one crystallization point that is the carbon fibre.

Table 1: Various heat treatments applied to C-PEEK composites

Isothermal Crystallization (IC)	Annealing (A + A)	Quenching + Annealing (Q + A)
As Received sample Slow heating, 10°C/min 380°C (6 min) Slow cooling, 10°C/min 150,200,250,310°C (40 min) Slow cooling, 10°C/min	As Received sample Slow heating, 10°C/min 150,200,250,310°C(0.5,1, 2,4 hour) Slow cooling, 10°C/min	Ouenched sample Slow heating, 10°C/min 150,200,250,310°C(0.5,1, 2,4 hour) Slow cooling, 10°C/min

WAXD scans were obtained using a Phillips 1050 vertical goniometer. Cross-ply laminate sections, 20 mm², were inserted into the sample holder and the diffraction profiles were recorded at a scanning rate of 0.02° 2θ min⁻¹ over an angular range of 12° < 2θ < 36°. The crystalline degrees are seen from Table 2,3,4.

Table 2: The crystallization degree of A+A samples

Annealing Temp. (°C)	30	60	120	240
150	17.99	19.25	20.50	22.10
200	21.02	21.25	21.68	22.38
250	17.93	17.75	17.40	17.22
310	23.94	23.50	23.00	21.96

Table 3: The crystallization degree of Q+A samples

Annealing Temp. (°C)	30	60	120	240
150	10.47	11.35	12.75	14.25
200	12.50	13.75	14.50	15.50
250	15.00	17.25	19.35	20.94
310	21.03	22.50	24.00	25.28

Table 4: The crystallization degree of IC samples

Crystallization Temperature (°C)	Degree of Crystallinity (%)
150	24.36
200	20.79
250	26.59
310	23.58

Impact Testing

Fracture toughness of the samples are investigated with a Charpy-V tester. The dimensions of the samples are 2.1×12×60 mm. Figure 1 gives the Charpy-V test results of IC, A+A and Q+A samples.

Figure 1: Fracture toughness values of samples

It is seen that the highest fracture toughness values are in IC samples but Table 4 shows that there isn't much increase in the degree of crystallinity in these samples with increasing heat treatment temperature. It is nearly same for A+A samples. The results shows that however the degree of crystallinity being equal, the type of the crystals play a significant role in fracture toughness. The more organized crystals formed by IC treatments results in better performance compared to these results from the annealing crystallization.

In Q+A samples, there is much residual stresses formed during quenching and these strongly affect the fracture toughness of the samples. Increase in annealing time, relieves these stresses and in turn, the fracture toughness values increase. Also it is clear that achieving good fibre-matrix interphase is very important for increasing the fracture toughness values, too. Q+A samples showed the largest changes with increasing annealing temperature being around 54 Kp.cm/cm² at 150°C and around 100 Kp.cm/cm² at 310°C.

At 310°C, the fracture toughness values of all samples are very close to each other. At this temperature, all samples show nearly same crystallinity, too. Although the same crystal form and microstructure, not given in this paper, these similarity in samples result with similar fracture toughness values.

Bending Test

Instron 1115 is used for bending tests. The dimensions of the sample is 2.1×10×60 mm. The span is 50 mm. The Q+A samples were used in three point bending tests to investigate the mechanical properties. In these samples crystallization occurs only in fibre surface. So the transcrystalline phase determine the mechanical properties of composite. Also to determine the role of crystallinity degree on mechanical properties, we choose the lowest crystallinity (Q+150 / 30 min.) and the highest one (Q+310 / 240 min.). The results are given in Table 5 and Figure 2.

Table 5: Three point bending test results

Q+A Samples	A	B	C
Flexural Strength (MPa)	880.2	972.8	1042.5
Increase in Flexural Strength (%)	-	10.5	18.43
Toughness (daN.mm)	50.55	52.388	62.093
Increase in toughness (%)	-	3.6	22.3
Flexural modulus (MPa)	83485	104544	91141

Figure 2: Bending test diagrams

CONCLUSIONS

It is seen that the crystallization degree is increased with the temperature and the time in annealing for quenched and as received samples. The mechanical properties are increased with crystallization degree. The type of crystals is very important for fracture toughness of composites. The three point bending test results show that the fibre/matrix interphase has a significant role on the performance of composites.

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